

Report on the development of scalable scientific workflows with integration of modular data-centric solutions

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Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the integration of data-centric solutions into scalable and automated workflows for the EERIE IFS-NEMO simulations. Building on the Climate-DT workflow, an EERIE-specific IFS-NEMO model version generates NetCDF output, which is subsequently joined, CMORized, and structured according to EERIE format tables. The entire process is automated via Autosubmit, from model compilation to dedicated postprocessing tasks and quality checks, ensuring that data are ready for further analysis or ESGF dissemination with minimal manual intervention. This approach enables seamless integration of online diagnostics and postprocessing into model simulations, reduces data transfer overhead, and supports reproducibility and operational efficiency. We also explain in this deliverable how the solutions described for this model and platform is portable to other use cases.

1. Workflow

1.1. Basic Purpose and Functionality

In EERIE we are taking advantage of the workflow of the Destination Earth Climate Digital Twin, which runs in different EuroHPC machines (Marenostrum 5 and LUMI, for example). The ClimateDT workflow is publicly available at <https://github.com/DestinE-Climate-DT/Workflow/>. In EERIE, we are modifying some of the scripts and configurations to take into account the scientific and technical specificities of each workflow.

At its core, the workflow orchestrates complex climate simulations by automating model compilation, execution, post-processing, data quality checks, and application workflows. It leverages Autosubmit4¹ to coordinate tasks and supports multiple operational modes:

- Model mode for pure climate model simulations.
- End-to-end mode to run models and applications in a streaming pipeline.
- Applications mode to simulate application processing without running a model.
- Simless mode to process existing data or manage ancillary jobs like backups and transfers.

The workflow supports modular customization via YAML configuration files, allowing users to select models, applications, platforms, resolutions, and job-specific settings dynamically.

¹ Manubens-Gil, D., Vegas-Regidor, J., Prodhomme, C., Mula-Valls, O., & J. Doblas-Reyes, F. (2016). Seamless management of ensemble climate prediction experiments on HPC platforms. 2016 International Conference on High Performance Computing & Simulation (HPCS), 895–900. <https://doi.org/10.1109/HPCSim.2016.7568429>

1.2. Jobs

1.2.1. Primary jobs

Depending on the workflow mode selected, different primary jobs will be executed. The jobs are what Autosubmit submits to the remote platforms. They are a combination of templates (bash scripts) and the configuration selected by the user.

The templates are located in `/workflow/templates`.

- **Local_setup**: Performs basic checks as well as compressing the workflow project in order to be sent through the network from the local machine to the HPC.
- **Synchronize**: Syncs the workflow project with the remote platform.
- **Remote_setup**: Loads the necessary environment.
- **Dvc setup**: Initializes DVC repository needed for model inputs.
- **Ini**: prepares any necessary initial data for the climate model runs. Runs in the login node of the HPC.
- **SIM**: Main script used to run the different climate models

Figure 1. Example of a model simulation workflow with Autosubmit4.

1.3. EERIE-specific jobs

1.3.1. Model-side specifications

To define the requirements for additional Autosubmit jobs for handling model output, it is essential to first understand the model specifications.

The EERIE IFS-NEMO simulations use a fixed bundle version, DE_CY48R1.0_EERIE_20240726, which relies on modified versions of ECMWF ecCodes 2.35.1 and MultIO 2.1.9. EcCodes is an ECMWF library that handles the encoding of grib files and MultIO is the model I/O library used. These modifications were specifically developed to enable direct NetCDF output from the model. In EERIE experiments, the model resolution is TCo1279 for IFS (the atmospheric component) and eORCA12 for NEMO (the ocean component).

Simulations are executed on 125 CPU nodes (including 3 I/O nodes for IFS and 2 I/O nodes for NEMO), achieving an average performance of 1.47 simulated years per day. All runs are managed via Autosubmit in 6-month chunks, facilitating modular execution and postprocessing.

1.3.2 Adaptations performed to MultIO and eccodes

When using the official tags, IFS-NEMO by default outputs GRIB messages. To facilitate, automate and speed up the analysis, and data sharing without duplicating data (and therefore save disk storage), we have enabled the direct writing of the data by the model in NetCDF. To enable direct NetCDF output, we adapted an existing ecCodes library, `grib_to_netcdf`, which is originally designed to handle GRIB files of any size. Furthermore, the model writes GRIB files by sequentially appending GRIB messages, where each message represents a field “quanta”, i.e., a single timestep for a specific field and level. As a result, the NetCDF pipeline produces one NetCDF file per field, timestep, and level. For example, a 6-month simulation chunk generates 6 NetCDF files for monthly surface fields, while 6-hourly pressure-level fields may result in up to ~14,000 files per field. This output structure creates a clear need for a robust postprocessing pipeline capable of combining, merging, CMORizing, and compressing the data in accordance with CF and CMOR conventions and based on the recommendations formulated in deliverable 11.2.

1.3.3. Setup of model output

The configuration of IFS-NEMO model output is managed through a set of YAML files, referred to as “plans”. These plans define the sequence of operations applied to each field, including interpolation, computation of statistics (e.g., averages), and encoding. Due to the model-side modifications described above, any change in encoding also requires corresponding updates to the MultIO YAML plans. An example of a MultIO yaml plan for NetCDF output is shown in **Figure A-1 in the Annex**.

To simplify management of the numerous YAML plans, an in-house Python tool called Autoplans was developed. Autoplans provides a single entry point for users to configure the full set of output plans efficiently. The tool leverages Jinja2 templates, allowing YAML files to include placeholders and logic, which enables flexible, automated generation of fully customized configuration files.

1.3.4 Model output storage

The total raw model output for a 6-month simulation chunk amounts to 975 GB, distributed as follows: 19 GB for monthly fields, 264 GB for daily output, 592 GB for 6-hourly output, and 102 GB for 3- and 1-hourly output, all on a regular $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ latitude-longitude grid. This volume corresponds to uncompressed data stored in double-precision format. After the postprocessing steps—which include converting variables from double to float and applying NetCDF compression—the total size is typically reduced by about 60%, depending on the variable characteristics and output frequency, as further described in the following sections.

1.3.5. EERIE-specific Autosubmit data reduction jobs

To manage the thousands of individual NetCDF files produced by the model and convert them to **CMOR- and CF-compliant EERIE standards**, a dedicated postprocessing infrastructure has been developed. This section provides an overview of the EERIE-specific Autosubmit jobs, with technical details described in later sections.

Following the **SIM** job, the following postprocessing jobs have been added:

- **EERIE_POSTPROC**: A Python-based workflow that collects and fixes raw model output into fully CMORized NetCDF files.

- **EERIE_CHECKER**: A separate Python tool that validates the NetCDF files, verifying folder structure, variable attributes, dimensions and other metadata requirements.
- **EERIE_CLEANER**: Once the previous jobs complete successfully, this job safely removes redundant raw NetCDF files, ensuring efficient storage usage.

This structured pipeline ensures that the raw model output is systematically processed, validated, and cleaned, enabling seamless integration into downstream analysis and ESGF (Earth System Grid Federation) submission workflows.

Figure 2. EERIE-specific model workflow with additional postprocessing tasks.

1.3.6. Granularity of postprocessing jobs

Although **Figure 2** shows a graph of the job dependencies, it is possible to adjust the granularity of the jobs to perform postprocessing on an already-completed simulation. In this case, Autosubmit would run in **“simless”** mode, and the resulting dependency graph could resemble **Figure 3**.

Figure 3. Example of the workflow running in “simless” mode, where each column represents the postprocessing pipeline of a simulation chunk.

In **Figure 3**, the postprocessing workflow is applied to a finished model simulation. The division of postprocessing jobs follows the number of simulation chunks, maintaining a structured and efficient execution.

Alternatively, a single pipeline could be used to process all model output at once, provided that sufficient computational resources and wallclock time are allocated. In this

configuration, the workflow would appear as a simpler, linear dependency graph. An example is shown in **Figure 4**.

At the other extreme, postprocessing could be organized per variable, maximizing parallelization. While this approach increases computational efficiency, it also significantly complicates the Autosubmit dependency graph, requiring careful management of task dependencies.

Figure 4. An example of a linear dependency processing pipeline. Useful to process a specific simulation chunk.

1.3.7. Resource usage in postprocessing jobs

An important consideration when configuring the postprocessing workflow for a simulation workflow is the model execution speed, quantified by the parameter simulated years per day (SYPD). For optimal performance, the time required to postprocess the

model output should be shorter than the time needed for the simulation to complete a single chunk.

On a single MareNostrum5 GPP node, postprocessing **975 GB** of raw output takes approximately 4 hours, which is faster than the model execution time of roughly 8 hours per chunk. In addition, this processing can be done while the next chunk of the simulation is run, reducing to close to 0, the additional time for processing compared to the simulation time.

As discussed in Section 1.3.6 regarding the granularity of postprocessing jobs, the computational resources and wallclock time allocated to each job can be adjusted depending on the chosen level of granularity, ensuring that the pipeline remains efficient and well-aligned with the simulation workflow.

2. Core of EERIE Postprocessing

A Python tool has been developed to manage the processing of raw model output data. Its primary objective is to CMORize the raw model output in accordance with the EERIE-specific CMOR tables. In other words, to enable efficient data sharing, the resulting NetCDF files must comply with the standards defined by the **CMIP6-style** JSON tables. For further details on the CMORization process, see **EERIE Deliverable D3.2 Publication of Phase 1 simulations**.

2.1. Introducing the challenge

As noted previously, the **volume of model output** combined with the raw output format presents significant challenges for data processing.

For example, in the simplest case of monthly surface fields, only six NetCDF files need to be combined and processed. However, as output frequency increases and vertical-level

fields are considered, the number of individual NetCDF files grows exponentially, reaching nearly 14,000 files for 6-hourly pressure-level fields. In these cases, a single merged file prior to compression can occupy 57 GB.

Furthermore, due to inherent model characteristics of IFS-NEMO—such as data variable type and latitude ordering—there is a clear need for a robust, automated Python-based software capable of efficiently handling, transforming, and CMORizing the model output.

2.2. Design of software

2.2.1. Input requirements

The postprocessing Python software requires basic experiment metadata, provided via an input YAML file, including: experiment ID (expid), simulation type, simulation start year, model name, and experiment description.

In addition, chunk-specific information must be supplied, such as chunk size, start date, end date, and the simulation run directory.

Finally, the software needs a link to the EERIE `dreq_tools` repository², which contains all relevant CMOR JSON tables required for the CMORization process.

2.2.2. Flow of code

The software initially reads the raw model output field information and stores it in a YAML file, referred to as the "portfolio." This approach eliminates the need to explicitly provide the model output, as the code can determine it automatically from the run directory. The portfolio describes key metadata for each output, including frequency, CMOR table,

² https://github.com/eerie-project/dreq_tools/

levtype, and short names.

Next, all CMOR tables are loaded into a cache. This optimization is important because repeatedly reading the JSON files can be computationally expensive when processing thousands of files, while the memory overhead of the cache is negligible.

The main loop of the code iterates over the different frequencies, CMOR tables, and variables to instantiate a `VariableProcessing` class. The structure allows either full processing of all output or selective processing of specific CMOR tables or variables. This is related to the discussion in section 1.3.6 regarding the granularity of workflow jobs.

The software also ensures that a folder structure compliant with the EERIE-specified output format exists, creating it if necessary. This is where the final processed fields are written.

Within the `VariableProcessing` module, three main functions are performed.

The first function is responsible for merging files, with different strategies depending on whether the field is two-dimensional or three-dimensional. For two-dimensional fields, datasets are opened lazily and concatenated along the time dimension, then rechunked to optimize the writing process.

Three-dimensional fields require a more complex approach due to the large number of files involved. The merging process is twofold: first along the vertical dimension and then along the time dimension. To parallelize this operation on the 112 cores of a GPP MareNostrum5 node, the `Pool` function from Python's multiprocessing module is used. Vertical level concatenation is performed in batches of 20 using 6 processes. These parameters were empirically determined to optimize memory and CPU usage. All files are opened lazily to prevent memory spikes, and the final datasets are merged along the time dimension. In this case, the dataset is rechunked to six time steps, including all vertical levels and latitude and longitude coordinates.

The second function is the dataset standardizer, implemented as a class method of `DatasetStandardizer`. This function modifies the xarray dataset to ensure compliance with required attributes, dimensions, variables, and data types. Scale factors are applied to

certain IFS-NEMO variables to convert units from the raw model output to those specified in the CMOR tables. Variable data types are changed from double to float, spatial coordinates are renamed according to CMOR standards, and latitudes are reordered from descending to ascending. Vertical atmospheric levels are converted from hectopascal to pascal, and ocean levels are converted to depth in meters. Additional adjustments, such as renaming auxiliary variables and updating attributes, are also applied following the CMOR JSON tables.

The final step in the VariableProcessing pipeline is the write function. This is the most computationally intensive step and represents the main bottleneck in the code. Various strategies were tested, including different chunking schemes, engines (netCDF4 and h5netcdf), and writing first to SSD before transferring to GPFS. The largest performance gain, however, was achieved by disabling compression. Although compression uses zlib with a deflate level of 1, compressing large files consumes significant CPU resources and can slow writing by up to seven times. As a result, compression is performed offline using optimized tools such as cdo and nccopy, allowing the main pipeline to run efficiently.

3. Data quality checker

The data quality checker was developed as part of a larger Python infrastructure designed to validate and fix files generated from raw model output.

The code follows a modular, class-based design, where all checks are derived from a base class called BaseCheck. Some checks are fixable, such as variable attributes, and are implemented via a derived class FixableCheck that includes the corresponding fix method. Other checks, such as AllTimestepsCheck, which verifies that all timesteps are present, are inherently non-fixable.

3.1. Input requirements

The input requirements are the same as those for the postprocessing code described in Section 2.2.1. An optional flag, `fix_issues`, can be provided if issues detected by the checker should be automatically corrected. However, within the workflow pipeline, the primary purpose of the software is data quality validation rather than automatic correction.

3.2. Output and checker result report

At the end of its execution, the checker produces a summary and detailed report listing all issues and their descriptions. If any issue is detected for a file, an error is logged, and the corresponding Autosubmit task is failed to prevent accidental data removal or propagation of invalid output.

3.3. Checker flow of code

An orchestrator class, `CheckRunner`, manages the execution of the different checks on every file found in the EERIE-structured folder output. Similar to the postprocessing workflow described in Section 2, a series of `Descriptor` objects is generated to provide metadata for each NetCDF file located in the inner folders.

For each `FileDescriptor`, the full set of checks is executed using a common class method named `run`. If a check identifies an issue, an `Issue` object is returned and tracked by a `Report` object.

The checks are categorized into three types: file-quality, NetCDF-quality, and physical-quality checks.

File-quality checks focus on file-specific format issues, such as verifying that filenames match the expected conventions, timestamps are correct, and the model name is present in the filename.

NetCDF-quality checks are more extensive, addressing issues commonly found in IFS-NEMO raw model output data. These include verifying variable types, dimensions, attributes, compression, time bounds, and other metadata requirements. For more details on the data standards that NetCDF files must follow, see **EERIE Deliverable D3.2 Publication of Phase 1 simulations**.

Physical-quality checks ensure that the data values and units are physically consistent. Some checks, such as temperature ranges, are straightforward, while others cannot be generalized and require case-specific validation.

Finally, it is worth noting that the `FixManager` object, which orchestrates the application of fixes to the data, is not described here. The main difference compared to the postprocessing workflow in Section 2 is that `FixManager` uses the lower-level Python module `netCDF4` to modify datasets and rewrite them when higher-complexity fixes are required.

4. Transferring of data

4.1. Transfer to `/esarchive/`

The model simulations are performed on MareNostrum5, with initial data stored on its GPFS filesystem. Given the large volume of model output and storage requirements—approximately 2 TB per simulation chunk before compression—the full dataset cannot be retained on GPFS. Therefore, the data must be transferred to the permanent storage facility at BSC, located at `/esarchive`. Currently, these transfers are performed manually using dedicated data-transfer nodes.

4.2. Transfer to Levante

Additional EERIE partners analyze the simulation data on the Levante system at DKRZ. Consequently, the simulation output is also transferred to Levante offline to provide access for collaborative analysis.

5. Portability

5.1. Across HPC systems

The Autosubmit climate DT workflow has been successfully deployed on multiple HPC ecosystems, including Marenstrum 5, and LUMI³.

The workflow orchestration itself requires a virtual machine that can access the platforms where the different parts of the workflow run. Autosubmit is installable through conda or pip, as described in the documentation⁴.

The postprocessing pipeline and the data quality checker are distributed within a Singularity container, which allows for straightforward deployment across different HPC environments. The container includes Python (version 3.11) along with other required libraries like xarray (version 2025.1.2) and netCDF4 (version 1.7.2).

5.2. Across models

The climateDT workflow has been used with other climate models such as IFS-FESOM and ICON. Integrating additional models is also possible and it consists of adding model-specific run scripts to the workflow jobs described in Section 1.2.1.

Regarding the postprocessing pipeline described in Section 2, certain steps, such as merging single NetCDF files, are currently specific to the IFS-NEMO model version. However, the file rebuilding phase, which creates the CMOR-compliant NetCDF outputs, is model-agnostic and can be applied to any type of NetCDF output.

³ <https://lumi-supercomputer.eu/>

⁴ <https://autosubmit.readthedocs.io/en/master/installation/index.html>

The data quality checker is also reusable across different models, provided that the model outputs follow the EERIE-specific output folder structure. While some checks are project-specific (because they depend on the EERIE CMOR tables or some internal conventions regarding for example the ordering of the latitudes and longitudes), the modular design allows for easy extension to accommodate new models or additional verification criteria.

The code is available in the BSC gitlab and can be made accessible on demand. The recipes of the containers follow the same approach. They are currently stored in Marenostrom 5 but can be shared.

6. Conclusions and future perspectives

The full automation and modularization of the workflow and data processing described in this deliverable shows, for one model, solutions to enhance and facilitate the data management by reducing the time-to-solution for the scientific analysis. Even if not described in this deliverable, the diagnostics for monitoring the simulation described in D11.2 “Report on the design and implementation of atmosphere, ocean and sea ice diagnostics, including their containerization”, including the containerized AQUA diagnostics, will also be integrated in the workflow of the coming EERIE IFS-NEMO simulation, using the data preparation and reduction described in this deliverable.

In addition, the workflow orchestration can easily be adapted to other models or infrastructure. In particular, in the framework of linking the EERIE and EDITO projects, some reduced versions or configurations of the EERIE workflow could be run in the EDITO infrastructure.

Annex

```

name: 4_1_SFC_Monthly_RegularLL_standardres_netcdf_Amon
actions:
  - type: select
    match:
      - levtype: sfc
        paramId: [79, 134, 137, 151, 164, 165, 166, 167, 174096, 207, 235]

  - type: metadata-mapping
    mapping: '{MULTIO_RAPS_PLANS_PATH}/EERIE_Plans/mapping-EERIE-monthly-means.yaml'
    overwrite-existing: true
    enforce-match: true

  - type: statistics
    output-frequency: 1m
    options:
      initial-condition-present: true
      step-frequency: 1
      time-step: 3600
      use-current-time: true
    operations:
      - average

  - type: interpolate
    input: '{MULTIO_RAPS_GRID_TYPE}'
    grid: [0.25, 0.25]
    area: [90.0,0.0,-90.0,360.0]
    interpolation: grid-box-average
    options:
      caching: true

  - type: encode
    format: grib
    template: '{MULTIO_RAPS_TEMPLATES_PATH}/templates.{MULTIO_RAPS_GRID_TYPE}/regular_ll_sfc_statistical_grib2.tmpl'
    additional-metadata:
      resolution: standard

  - type: sink
    sinks:
      - type: netcdf
        enable: '{MULTIO_ENABLE_SINK_FILE}'
        append: false
        per-server: true
        netcdf_message_buffer: 1
        CMOR_table: Amon
        path: '{MULTIO_RAPS_OUTPUT_PATH}/02-InterpolatedGrid/04-Monthly/sfc_MONTHLY_'

```

Figure A-1. Example of a MultiO plan for EERIE netcdf output.

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